

THE MODERN TEACHER AND HIS IMAGE

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy pedagog va uning obrazi, o'qituvchi shaxsiga qo'yiladigan talablar va hozirgi zamon o'qituvchisi qanday bo'lishi kerakligi yoritib berilgan. Pedagogik mahorat o'qituvchi sifatining muhim tarkibiy qismi. Til bilimdonligi haqida ham to'xtalib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Zamonaviy o'qituvchi, obraz, notiq, pedagogik muloqot ijodiy, pedagogik mahorat.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается о современном педагоге и его имидже, о требованиях к учителю и о том, каким должен быть современный педагог. Педагогическое мастерство является важной составляющей качества учителя. Обсуждались и языковые навыки.

Ключевые слова: Современный учитель, имидж, спикер, педагогическое общение, творчество, педагогическое мастерство.

Abstract: This article describes the modern teacher and his image, the requirements for the teacher's personality and what a modern teacher should look like. Pedagogical skills are an important part of a teacher's quality. Linguistics is also mentioned.

Keywords: Modern teacher, image, speaker, pedagogical communication creative, pedagogical skills.

Introduction. The teacher's role is described beyond teaching. They are more than an educator and are counselors, mentors, role models, external parents, and so on to a student. There are many significance ways that providing a better understanding of a lesson to helpful for students in better future. A teacher is like a burning candle. It

burns itself and illuminates the surroundings broadcasts. It is known that all professions are first taught by a teacher. teacher - he is a teacher who teaches, guides, educates. Initial the teacher also gives the lesson. The meaning of the original motherland words, the teacher also teaches the essence. That's why in all professions the teaching profession is very honorable and responsible.

Methods of analysis. The new teaching method which we called the modern teaching method is more activity-based and centres the learner's mind which involves them entirely into the process of learning. In the modern teaching method, curriculum teaching and planning are done keeping the learner as the primary target. Through this way, learners actively participate in the whole process to build their knowledge and sharpen their skills; this is also termed as a constructivist approach.¹¹ On the other hand, the mentor or teacher only leads them and guides them to focus on the objectives of the subject. This is all done by engaging in activities and by adopting innovative modern teaching techniques. New demand of the era or the need of the hour for students is to embrace the contemporary teaching methods which will also help in reducing the competition among the students, promote cooperation, and boost the health study environment. The traditional methods of teaching are still prevalent in most parts of our nation. In educational institutions, teachers are the only source to gain information. Teachers explain the concept to the learners with the use of blackboard and chalk.¹² They write all the content on the blackboard and ask the students to note down in their notebooks and memorize and recite the notes. All the focus of education in these institutions is to pass the semester.

Literature analysis. Teaching profession is a highly honorable profession. This profession is not a profession. The famous Russian pedagogue A.S. Makarenko is very high on the teaching profession evaluates and defines it as follows: "He should know how to joke, be cheerful or angry, he should behave like that it is necessary that his every action, behavior, and dress should educate children". This from the definition it can be concluded that the pedagogue is perfect in all aspects, should be an ideal person for students. Even the dress of the teacher raise the children. Teachers are in the process of communication with students, parents and colleagues it is appropriate for them to

¹¹ Burkhanova M.G. (2021). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL LOOK OF A CULTURAL MAN. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.02.94.6> Doi:

¹² Burkhanova M.G. (2021). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL LOOK OF A CULTURAL MAN. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.02.94.6> Doi:

focus on expressing their opinion clearly and succinctly. In the process of dealing with them, from giving evidence about negative situations does not start, on the contrary, students (or colleagues, parents) by acknowledging their successes and expressing confidence in further enriching them should organize communication. From the teacher's words during the dialogue benevolence, sincerity, friendly attitude towards the interlocutor, good mood let it be noticeable. The image of the teacher that meets these requirements is his to gain respect among students, colleagues and parents provides.¹³

Results and analysis. In the current conditions, the demands of the society on the teaching profession are increasing day by day, and the task of properly organizing these demands in practice depends on the teacher. A modern school teacher performs a number of tasks. The teacher is primarily the organizer of the educational process in the classroom. A teacher as an educator should know the following requirements:

- national revival in the spiritual and educational upbringing of a person;
- knowing the essence of the ideology and universal wealth, raising children in the spirit of loyalty to the ideals of independence, love for their motherland, nature and family;
- to be aware of various knowledge along with thorough knowledge of professional knowledge;
- perfect knowledge of youth pedagogical psychology, pedagogy and psychology, youth physiology, educational work methodology, school hygiene;
- to be constantly aware of the latest achievements in world science, education technology, computer and information technologies, news in his profession;
- to improve skills and qualifications of educational methods;
- creative approach to his profession;
- to have pedagogical technique (logic, expressive means of speech education) and pedagogical tact;
- constantly improving his knowledge and pedagogical skills.

Every teacher must have pedagogical skills to work successfully. The main rule of pedagogical skill is to achieve great results with little effort. Creativity will always be his companion.¹⁴ Pedagogical skills are formed only in a capable, talented person

¹³ Fyerbyerman “Ilg`or pedagogik texnologiya” T. 2000-y.

¹⁴ Burkhanova M.G. (2022). AXIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF STUDENT MORALITY. European journal of research development and sustainability. Vol 3 N 2. <https://www.scholarzest.com/>

who is interested in pedagogical activities. Pedagogical activity has a creative nature according to its essence. The teacher forms the personality of the student, makes independent decisions in unexpected situations, solves pedagogical problems, independently manages the educational process. All this is related to the essence of creativity, the purpose and character of the work. Only a teacher with pedagogical skills. He achieves great success in his professional activities.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that a modern pedagogue should have deep knowledge of his subject, have pedagogical skills, and also know foreign languages. For example, a primary school teacher should know English at least partially, if not perfectly. The reason is that the units of measurement are included in the new edition of mathematics textbooks for primary grades in English. The teacher must be able to explain this to the child, for this he must be familiar with the English language. Knowledge of language is also necessary for a pedagogue to work with modern computer technologies and smart boards.

References:

1. I.A.Karimov “Buyuk kelajagimizning huquqiy kafolati” – Toshkent Sharq nashriyoti
2. A.Xoliqov “Pedagogik mahorat” – Toshkent-2011y.
3. B.X.Xodjayeva “Umumiy pedagogika” – Toshkent-2017y.
4. Burkhanova M.G. (2022). AXIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF STUDENT MORALITY. European journal of research development and sustainability. Vol 3 N 2. <https://www.scholarzest.com/>
5. Burkhanova M.G. (2021). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL LOOK OF A CULTURAL MAN. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 12 (104), 422-425. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS.2021.02.94.6> Doi:
6. Fyerbyerman “Ilg`or pedagogik texnologiya” T. 2000-y.
7. N. Azizxadjayeva “Pedagogik texnologiya” T. 2001-y.